

Stakeholder engagement event: Royal Highland Show

Feedback notes from engagement on animal disease control: barriers and challenges

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Introduction

During the Royal Highland Show 2024 a collaborative stakeholder engagement event was co-hosted by EPIC, James Hutton Institute and Moredun Research Institute. Farmers, crofters, industry and Scottish government representatives were invited to attend and provide feedback and reflection of animal disease control within island based livestock holdings.

Executive summary

- Farmers noted the importance of being involved in long term projects on disease control particularly around bought in animals
- Peer-to-peer exchanges are valuable and have helped make topics such as disease control easier to openly discuss.
- Facilitation and space to talk openly should be prioritised
- Collaboration within islands, townships and communities needs to be fostered and enhanced
- Practical logistics of animal disease control can help future planning on islands
- Communities felt empowered to bring about changes in managing animal disease
- Networking between islands can open links to share experiences and provide practical advice
- Long-term schemes need investment for co-ordination, e.g. a dedicated project officer to introduce and manage collaborations and interventions
- Planned legacy beyond the life of a project needs careful consideration and financing
- A strong coordination team is essential to deliver an animal disease control campaign

Feedback from discussion groups

Sheep scab control

- Attendees discussed the risks posed from bought in animals and neighbouring farms/livestock. There was a strong feeling that they were always at the mercy of the weakest link in the chain. Some described a feeling of being powerless to control sheep scab, and other diseases, on an island croft.
- Bringing the discussion on animal disease to an open group, especially sheep scab, had helped address issues.
- Collective and collaborative efforts have led to improvements in tackling sheep scab control.
- The visit of Lewis and Harris crofters to Shetland helped reinforce feelings of positivity, resulting in an empowered group
- Legacy of the long-term projects will lead to improved future animal disease control

Roundworm control

- Peer-to-peer learning is a good way to get messages heard. This could include farmer advocates to talk to sceptical farmers to explain the benefits. “Good Farmer” and “Roadside Farming”.
- Involve farmers’ organisations and groups in training and supporting networks – the importance of the social side was highlighted, often mediated by technologies to keep in contact.
- Advisers can help farmers to move away from firefighting e.g. with worm control based on set treatment times, towards preventative management based on diagnostics such as faecal egg counts (FEC) etc. Vets need to encourage farmers to do FEC and provide training and support.

Importance of long-term investment into management -

- Farmers need to be involved in long-term projects (three years plus) to be able to see the benefits of using animal disease control methods
- Long-term schemes need more investment on the coordination side, e.g. dedicated project officers, to introduce and manage quarantine procedures.
- All advisers and other actors could frame animal health management as part of the big issues on farm, e.g. business management. Following a whole farm system to “Farm smarter” i.e. managing worms means less work for the farmer, and an easier life.
- The legacy of projects is important to consider. This has more than just an animal health dimension, it also impacts the communities working towards animal health goals.
 - Messaging; some felt that there is confusing and conflicting advice from different advisers whilst others felt that there are too many similar messages, presented in similar ways, coming from government, which turned farmers off

Island animal disease control

- The importance of willingness to engage and the known impacts of animal health schemes should be widely shared
- Strong partnerships between the actors involved are important to ensure collaboration especially around disease control and cooperation
- The possibility of using tenancy agreements to enforce animal disease control could be explored for tenanted livestock keepers or those in a national park
- Simple guidelines, that are easy to follow, are essential for good animal disease control
- Passionate leaders and strong characters can help coordinate a good campaign

A question was posed to the researchers: What could/should the Scottish government be funding?

- Mobile dippers and handling systems
- Improved fencing
- Resources to assist in coordination and pan-island activities
- Train the trainer events

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